

EFFECTIVENESS OF MULTIMEDIA E- BOOK FOR TEACHING SECONDARY LEVEL SCHOOL - A STUDY

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1. ABSTRACT :

Education is ongoing process throughout the life. In 21st century the world is rapidly growing and changing; to cope up with this modern education system is also changing rapidly. Together with changes new expectation appeared towards teacher from the society as a part of which teacher's role is also changing as per.

All the developed and developing nations are focusing on the improvement, generation and sharing of the knowledge and also the flow of the new technology along with our country. In the national and international policy debates the proper knowledge occupies the central stage, in the age of productivity and innovation.

Education fields include teaching – learning, research and management. For good teaching-learning practice, it should be interactive which need large amount of information. Computer is in the best storage for such huge information which can easily get used for different purpose.

Using E- book as textbooks in classroom at school is a new paradigm especially in developing countries. E- Book offers students, teacher and school an additional medium or tool of instruction that enhance learning process. And so the present research work can provide useful to the field of education as well as for nation too.

In the changing world as education system is changing, it needs new things to be get integrated in the education teaching learning process. So E-book containing multimedia is used for the teaching purpose at every stage of education system along with secondary level.

Key words : - Education, innovation, E- book, Multimedia etc.

2. INTRODUCTION :

In the rapidly changing world the concept of education system is also changing which ultimately needed the changed and more powerful role of teachers. Teacher is important part of the educational systems in which role of the teacher is not only having subject related knowledge but teacher should perform the multitasking role like mentor, tutor, Guide, philosopher provider and also role model for students.

The modern age regarded as a time in which information has become a valuable thing that is quickly and disseminate and easily available especially through the use of computer technology which is used worldwide. Exploration of new technology advancement in present machinery or technology is the specialty of this age. Also computerization is the major factor.

Education fields include teaching – learning process, research and management. For good teaching – learning practice, it should be interactive which need large amount of information. Computer is the best storage for such huge information which can easily get used for different purpose. Also for the good interaction and effective teaching, good quality of communication is needed.

This is new and distinct period of time, in which technology affects all activities of our lives, especially the younger generation who were born post- internet, the education system is in the revetment of confront to adopt to the technological developments of the 21st century.(Hamedi & Ezleila,2015)

Today’s educational system must provide lifelong learners who are able to process large amount knowledge every day. The traditional educational system is teacher centered. In this system students receive knowledge only transmitted by the teacher and somewhat from book which is out dated now. Thus, the good students are those who have good listening skills, take note summarizing contents and passed in the test. On the other hand in the students need to be independent and lead themselves , react very actively to solve the problem, and acts as generator of knowledge in the 21st century that should be adjusted to the student’s own learning goals.(Hamedi & Ezleila,2015)

3. CONCEPTIONAL AND OPERATIONAL DEFINATIONS OF THE TERMS :

The operational definitions of the term include in the statements as follows:

1. Effectiveness :

Effectiveness refers to the level of quality with which a task or process is carried out that ultimately leads to higher overall performance, means does it do what it’s supposed to do? Effectiveness also defines as, “The degree to which something is successful in producing a desired result , success.

The proposed paper aims to take sample students from schools for the experimental purpose from proposed limited area.

2. Multimedia E- book :

As the name suggest, multimedia is the integration of multiple forms of media. Multimedia assigns to computerized information that is presented contemporaneously in more than one medium. It consists not necessarily all but sometimes few elements, of the following elements: text; still graphic images, motion graphics, animations, hyper media, photographs, video and audio i.e. sound, music and narration and so on many more.

E-book is short for “electronic book”. It is a digital publication that can be read on a computer, e-reader or other electronic device by the reader.

In this paper multimedia E-book studies any subject to study its effectiveness at secondary level for any subject which we referred and prepared.

3. Secondary level schools:

A school intermediate between elementary school and college and usually offering general, technical, vocational, or college- preparatory courses. In other word. A secondary school might also be known as a high school or as an academy. It usually provides educational instruction for students during the period from ages 11 to 18.

In this paper students consider from the secondary level school.

4. OBJECTIVES OF THE RESEARCH :

- 1 To develop E- book to teach at Secondary level for any subject we preferred.
- 2 To study the effectiveness of E- book in teaching at secondary level on students performance after using.
- 3 To compare the effectiveness of conventional method of teaching and E- book method for teaching.

5. EFFECTIVENESS OF MULTIMEDIA E-BOOK FOR TEACHING :

The main purpose of the present study was to observe effectiveness of multimedia E- Book instructional system on the for secondary level students and to see its effectiveness on the performance of the students.

Multimedia technique was used to develop the instructional system;

The following paragraphs show the effectiveness of multimedia E- Book for teaching of present research.

- 1 Teaching of any subject at secondary level in school with the help of multimedia E- book is more effective and better then teaching even any subjects through conventional teaching method.
- 2 The academic achievement performed by students are more through multimedia E- book and got better result in every subject then the students taught through conventional teaching method.
- 3 The academic achievement performed by students in retention test is also better where subjects taught with the help of multimedia E-book then the general conventional method.

These findings of the study completely indicated that the multimedia E-book help to the student for more academic achievement, more will to study, better environment for learning process and retention memory.

6. DISCUSSION OF RESULTS :

According to the theory of constructivism, knowledge is not taught but it is created and learned by the learner himself through constructing new knowledge on the bases of old knowledge with the help of others, such as teacher's or study partners under a certain setting, by utilizing certain study recourses so the students should be the centre of teaching in the process of education and student centered methodology should be used for the teaching in modernized world. Teachers should understand the need of students and try to meet with those needs. So from the point of view of this paper, multimedia assisted teaching approach can help students. Learn in a better way.

It cannot be denied that multimedia assisted approach can make every subject more interesting, and to some extent, to change the situation of having to learn in to willing to learn. Multimedia E-book combines audio, video, graphics, images and text together and it offers a brilliant colorful dramatic, direct study environment. It consists of different kinds of forms, activities and exercises. It can engage the students in the learning process and enhance the student's interests for learning.

It can facilitate any subject in teaching and learning process and make it more efficient and well equipped. Well designed multimedia E-book containing information of all concepts given in the complete subject curricula can provide students with the lot of useful information such as word study, organization of the text, language structures, useful expressions, sentence explanations, cultural background. With the just click of a mouse and students can present the visual information, with the help of hyper media student get connected with new information the students needed easily efficiently, saving a lot of time otherwise used in lecturing an blackboard writing as per conventional or traditional method used till now every now and then.

Teacher educator is a very important of a class who does the beneficial things for the students in class like: To explain difficult parts to act as source of information, to design some activities to analyze if students have really grasped the knowledge they should learn, and by conducting the activity like group discussion, giving them some topics to discuss, debating, dialogue , personal response or by doing other things, such as debate and role playing.

This paper has proven that teaching and learning with multimedia E-book instruction is more effective than general or conventional or traditional teaching instruction with text book in terms of student's achievements and retention. Despite, there are defender that claim learning process is influenced more by the content and instructional strategy in a medium use by teacher educator in teaching process than by the type of medium get used (Schramm, 1977) and it is also claimed that media are simply a vehicles that deliver instruction during teaching but do not influence students achievement and academic gain. (Clark, 1983),

Still the effectiveness of teaching with multimedia E-book instruction system cannot be denied. Teacher educator should take advantage and benefit of multimedia teaching instruction not only to teach but also to create environment where students wish to learn with joy and enhance student's motivations interest and achievement.

In order to evaluate the impact of using multimedia E- book on education a descriptive and narrative as well as mixed or mingled research methodology is designed.

To study the effectiveness of multimedia E- book, one should can carry out retention test for more result to see for further discussion, conclusion, and recommandations.

7. CONCLUSION :

As we have already stated that the effect of conventional method is cannot denied, but a combination of skills and experience of teacher educator and the use of multimedia teaching instruction will definitely bring about a more effective teaching and learning.

8. REOMMENDATION :

1. It is suggested that self learning material be developed for every secondary level teacher while teaching.
2. It is suggested that self learning material is used for every secondary level student while learning.
3. Multimedia E-book is necessity of the teachers for secondary level to show more effect for teaching and learning process.
4. The preparation of audio, visual and audio- visual teaching aids workshop should be a part and parcel of Educational Technology paper.
5. The teacher- educator should have proper understanding of the subject which they studied and without proper understanding of the subject; one cannot explain multimedia technology approach.
6. The teacher should comprehend the concept of development of multimedia E-book for any subject at any level of educational system.

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